

Spectrophotometric Study of Copper-salicylate Chelate

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The reaction between Cu(II) and salicylic acid has been investigated by spectrophotometry. The molecular composition has been studied by Job's method. The stability constants at different pHs, ionic strengths, and temperatures have been determined. The free energy, entropy, and enthalpy changes for the formation have been calculated. The thermodynamic stability constant has been obtained by various extrapolation methods.

In continuation of our studies on different chelates, formed by salicylic acid and its derivatives with various bivalent and trivalent metal ions, we have studied the nature of the olive-green complex formed by the interaction of Cu(II) and salicylic acid. Although Babko¹ studied the system at 20°, he did not maintain the ionic strengths of the solutions. In the present communication we have determined the stability constants of copper-salicylic acid complex at different ionic strengths and temperatures with a view to obtaining the thermodynamic quantities like ΔH and ΔS of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving E. Merck sample of copper carbonate in dilute perchloric acid (E. Merck., G. R.). It was estimated by iodometry.

E. Merck (G. R.) salicylic acid was dissolved in double distilled water to prepare the stock solution. It was estimated by titration against a standard alkali.

Absorption measurements were made with a Hilger-Watt 'UVISPEK' spectrophotometer, using quartz cells of 1 cm and 3 cm path length. pH adjustments were done with a battery-operated Marconi pH-meter (model TF 511 D). All other experimental details were the same as described in our earlier communications².

DISCUSSION

As a preliminary study, absorption spectra of both copper perchlorate and the mixture containing copper perchlorate and salicylic acid were run in the visible region of the spectrum at different pH values. Neither copper perchlorate nor the complex has any definite absorption maximum over the wave length range used. At lower pHs (below 3.5), absorption curves of copper perchlorate and the mixture almost coincide, suggesting

1. *J. Gen. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1947, 17, 443.

2. Aditya *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 473; 1960, 37, 557; 1961, 38, 19.

practically no complex formation. The extent of complex formation becomes appreciable at pH 4.0 or above. The stability constants of the complex were therefore determined at pH 4.0 and 4.5. At higher pH values, pH adjustments were found to be difficult in unbuffered solutions.

Molecular Composition of the Complex.—Job's method³ of continued variation was followed to determine the molecular composition of the complex. Absorbances of two

FIG. 1

sets of solutions at pH 4.5, containing different proportions of copper perchlorate and salicylic acid, keeping the total molarities constant at 1.287×10^{-2} and 1.716×10^{-2} , were measured at 750, 700, and 650 $m\mu$. Fig. 1 shows Job's curve at 750 $m\mu$ for both the molarities. The positions of the maxima of the curves at all the wave lengths indicate the complex formation to be of 1:1 type at pH 4.5. At lower pH s, the probability of any other complex (1:2 or 1:3) existing in solution is very small.

Extinction Coefficient.—The extinction coefficient of copper perchlorate was determined by measuring the absorbances of solutions of different concentrations, with pH s adjusted at definite values, at 750 $m\mu$. The values of extinction coefficients at the above wave length are found to be $9.91 (\pm 0.01)$ and $10.04 (\pm 0.01)$ at pH 4.0 and 4.5 respectively.

The extinction coefficient of the complex was determined in the same way as in our earlier publications². Absorbances of solutions of different concentrations of copper perchlorate and sodium salicylate, taken in large excess (1.15 to 1:30), with pH adjusted at desired values, were measured at 750 $m\mu$. In presence of this excess of salicylate, since the absorbance was constant for a particular concentration of the metal ion, concentrations of the complex were taken to be equal to those of copper perchlorate. The values of extinction coefficients of the complex at 750 $m\mu$ are $27.56 (\pm 0.05)$ and $31.25 (\pm 0.08)$ at pH 4.0 and 4.5 respectively.

Stability Constant.—The stability constant of the complex:

$$K = \frac{[\text{Complex}]}{\{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{Complex}]\} \{[\text{Sal}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{Complex}]\}}$$

has been calculated as in our earlier papers² at different pH s and ionic strengths. For this, absorbances of solutions containing copper perchlorate and the ligand with pH adjusted at 4.0 and 4.5 were measured at wave length 750 $m\mu$. Sodium perchlorate was added to these to fix the ionic strengths. The ionic strengths of the solutions were calculated

from the concentrations of sodium perchlorate, the reactants, and the complex. The average ionic strength for each set of solutions, which differed from the ionic strengths of individual solutions within a very small range, was taken to be the ionic strength for the set.

Table I records the stability constants at pH 4.0 and 4.5 and at different ionic strengths at room temperatures. The results show that stability constant decreases with an increase in the ionic strength, as expected; but beyond ionic strength 0.2, the value of K slightly increases. Such a slight increase (or almost constant value) is probably due to the fact that the activity coefficient of an ion passes through a minimum as the ionic strength increases.

TABLE I

Ionic strength.	No. of readings.	Wave length = 750 m μ .	Cell width = 3 cm.	Average stability constant.
		Conc. of the reactants.		
A. pH = 4.0. Temp. = 23				
0.08	7	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 4.272, 5.340, 5.874, 6.408 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.942, 7.476, 3.738 \end{array} \right.$		57.6 (± 1.3)
0.12	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 4.272, 4.806, 5.340, 5.874, 6.408 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.942, 7.476, 3.738, 3.204 \end{array} \right.$		50.1 (± 1.6)
0.20	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 4.272, 4.806, 5.340, 5.874, 6.408 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.942, 7.476, 3.738, 3.204 \end{array} \right.$		42.6 (± 2.0)
0.5	8	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 4.272, 4.806, 5.340, 5.874, 6.408 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 7.476, 3.738, 3.204 \end{array} \right.$		46.3 (± 1.9)
B. pH = 4.5. Temp. = 30°.				
0.02	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 7.2, 8.4, 6.0, 6.0, 7.2 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.888, 5.888, 5.888, 6.624, 6.624 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 8.4, 6.0, 7.2, 9.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.624, 5.152, 5.152, 6.624 \end{array} \right.$		2.04 (± 0.09) $\times 10^3$
0.08	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 7.2, 8.4, 6.0, 6.0, 7.2 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.888, 5.888, 5.888, 6.624, 6.624 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 8.4, 6.0, 7.2, 9.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.624, 5.152, 5.152, 6.624 \end{array} \right.$		1.84 (± 0.06) $\times 10^3$
0.12	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 8.4, 6.0, 6.0, 7.2, 8.4 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.888, 5.888, 6.624, 6.624, 6.624 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 6.0, 7.2, 8.4, 9.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.152, 5.152, 5.152, 6.624 \end{array} \right.$		1.61 (± 0.06) $\times 10^3$

TABLE I (contd.)

Ionic strength.	No. of reading.	Conc. of the reactants.	Average stability constant.
0.2	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 7.2, 8.4, 6.0, 6.0, 7.2 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.888, 5.888, 5.888, 6.624, 6.624 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 6.0, 7.2, 8.4, 9.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.152, 5.152, 5.152, 6.624 \end{array} \right.$	$1.53 (\pm 0.05) \times 10^3$
0.5	10	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 7.2, 8.4, 6.0, 6.0, 7.2 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 5.888, 5.888, 5.888, 6.624, 6.624 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 6.4, 6.0, 7.2, 6.4, 9.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.624, 5.152, 5.152, 5.152, 6.624 \end{array} \right.$	$1.58 (\pm 0.07) \times 10^3$

A comparison of the stability constants at the corresponding ionic strengths at pH 4.0 and 4.5 shows that these are clearly different. Incorporation of hydrogen-ion concentration at its first power in the numerator provides the value of ' K ', which are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

pH.	$K [\text{H}^+]$ at			
	0.08 μ .	0.12 μ .	0.2 μ .	0.5 μ .
4.0	0.576×10^{-2}	0.501×10^{-2}	0.426×10^{-2}	0.463×10^{-2}
4.5	0.580×10^{-2}	0.509×10^{-2}	0.484×10^{-2}	0.500×10^{-2}

The agreement between the values is quite good, considering experimental limitations. This suggests that only one proton is liberated during chelation. The reaction can therefore be written as

where HR^- stands for $\text{HO.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{COO}^-$.

It will be interesting to compare our results with that of Babko¹. He reported the formation constant ' K' ' of the reaction :

(R^{2-} stands for $^-\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{COO}^-$), which is related to the equilibrium constant ($K = [\text{CuR}] / [\text{Cu}^{2+}] [\text{HR}^-]$) on our presentation of the equilibrium, by the expression :

$$K' = \frac{K [\text{H}^+]}{K_d}$$

where K' is the constant on Babko's representation, K on ours, and K_d is the second dissociation constant of salicylic acid. Since there is no mention of ionic strength in Babko's work, we take the value of K determined by us at any arbitrary ionic strength for comparison. For ionic strength 0.08 and pH 4.5, $\log K'$ is 10.88 (second dissociation constant of salicylic acid is taken from the work of Ågren⁴). Thus our value of $\log K' = 10.88$ is of the

same order as that reported by Babko ($\log K' = 10.6$). A quantitative comparison between the two results is not possible.

Thermodynamic Stability Constant.—Thermodynamic stability constant of the complex was obtained by different methods of extrapolation. Plots of $\log K$ against μ and $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$ provided nonlinear curves.

An attempt was made to apply the Hitchcock⁷ type of extrapolation to this system using the Davies⁸ semi-empirical equation. The equation for the reaction between Cu^{2+} and salicylic acid can be written as

At constant pH,

$$K_T = \frac{a_{\text{CuR}}}{a_{\text{Cu}^{2+}} a_{\text{HR}^-}} = \frac{[\text{CuR}]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] [\text{HR}^-]} \cdot \frac{1}{f_{\frac{+}{-}} f_{\frac{-}{+}}} = K \times \frac{1}{f_{\frac{+}{-}} f_{\frac{-}{+}}}$$

Substituting for activity coefficient from the Davies equation:

$$-\log f_i = Az_i^2 \left(\frac{1}{1 + \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}} - C\mu \right)$$

and rearranging, we get

$$\log K + 5A \frac{\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \log K_T + 5AC\mu$$

which has the form of an equation of a straight line. We plotted

$$\log K + 5A \frac{\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

against μ , which gave nonlinear curves; but on plotting against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$ we surprisingly got straight lines. We have observed an exactly similar behaviour in connection with our studies on other chelates of salicylic acid, its derivatives and catechol disulphonic acid^{5,6}.

Recently Frank and Thompson⁹ have suggested that $\log f_{\pm}$ for an ion would be proportional to the cube root of concentration ($C^{\frac{1}{3}}$). We therefore plotted $\log K$ against $\mu^{\frac{1}{3}}$, which provided straight lines.

The values of K_T , obtained by different types of extrapolations, are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Type of plot.	Log K_T at pH 4.0.	Log K_T at pH 4.5.
Log K against μ	1.97	2.35
Log K against $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$	2.0	2.39
Log K against $\mu^{\frac{1}{3}}$	2.1	2.41
Log $K + 5A \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$ against	2.23	2.59
Log $K + 5A \frac{\sqrt[3]{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt[3]{\mu}}$ against $\sqrt[3]{\mu}$	2.11	2.47

5. R. K. Nanda, Ph. D. thesis, 1931, Utkal University, Cuttack.

6. R. C. Das, Ph. D. thesis, 1934, Utkal University.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2078.

8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.

9. "The Structure of Electrolytic Solution", edited by W. J. Hamer, John Wiley Publication, p. 113, 1959.

Since it is difficult to make a choice of the best type of extrapolation, we have recorded the results obtained by all the methods.

Entropy and Enthalpy Changes.—In view of the difficulty in obtaining the thermodynamic stability constant (hence ΔF°), we have determined the entropy and enthalpy changes at a fixed ionic strength. The stability constant of the complex at pH 4.0 and 0.2 ionic strength at 15° and 25°, apart from the result at the room temperature of 23°, are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Temp.	No. of readings.	Conc. of reactants used.	Average stability constant	$\Delta F (= RT \ln K)$
pH = 4.0. Wave length = 750 m μ Cell width = 3 cm. Ionic strength = 0.2.				
15° (± 0.1)	7	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 4.272, 5.340, 5.874 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.408, 7.476, 3.738 \end{array} \right.$	34.4 (± 1.5)	-2.02 (± 0.03)
23° (± 0.5)	9	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0 \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 3.204 \\ \text{Same as in Table I} \end{array} \right.$	42.6 (± 2.0)	-2.21 (± 0.03)
35° (± 0.1)	7	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 4.272, 5.340, 5.874 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 6.408, 7.476, 3.738 \\ [\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times 10^3 = 5.0. \\ [\text{H}_2\text{R}] \times 10^3 = 3.204. \end{array} \right.$	50.0 (± 2.5)	-2.39 (± 0.03)

From the slope of the curve, obtained on plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 2), ΔH of the reaction has been calculated to be 3.10 (+0.5) kcal. Assuming this to be constant over the range of experimental temperature, ΔS of the reaction has also been calculated and the value is 17.8 (± 2.0) e.u.

FIG. 2

Values of these thermodynamic functions show that the stability of the complex is mainly due to the entropy increase similar to our observations^{5,6} on chelates of salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids with Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , and Be^{2+} and those of catechol disulphonic acid with Ga^{3+} and In^{3+} .

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